

Digital Literacy And Undergraduate Students Attitude Towards Utilization Of Internet In Federal College Of Education (Technical), Omoku, Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study was carried out to investigate the relationship between digital literacy and undergraduates' students Attitude towards utilization of the internet in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku in Affiliation with University of Uyo. This study was guided by two research questions using browsing assignment and watching video as the study independent variables in relation to student digital literacy in internet utilization. Ex-post facto design was adopted for this study and the sample size consisted of two hundred (200) degree students who were drawn using random samplings. Data from this study were obtained using an instrument titled "Digital Literacy and Attitudes of Undergraduates in Internet Utilization Questionnaire" (DLAUIUQ). Information elicited from the instrument were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions. The finding revealed that majority of the undergraduates of Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku are conversant with the use of internet, which by extension influences their attitude towards using the internet for different purposes including academic, communication, entertainment and others. It was as a result of the above findings that the study recommended among others that; the college authorities should improve the quality of the internet services in the college and provide proper and thorough orientation on the necessity of internet knowledge, skills and application for students, so that they can gain from the massive benefits accrued to internet utilization.

Keywords: Digital literacy, Undergraduate Students, Student's Attitudes, Utilization of Internet

INTRODUCTION

Development in technology in recent years has grown rapidly having a lot of impact on the lives of humans. As technology grows, there are many ways that it can be applied to different areas including education. There are many technological advances that have changed the world of education in the 21st

century. These different technologies used in the classroom and school environment have a vast impact on the overall education of students around the world and their behaviors as well. The advancement in technology has led to the era of learning through the internet. Undeniably, the use of internet has grown rapidly in the educational system especially up to the tertiary level. Internet use has become a way of life in higher institutions of learning including Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku where information can be obtained easily with just one click of a mouse. Internet has simplified the way lecturers and teachers reach their students and it has also helped students learn from anywhere as well as enable them access to academic information at anytime from anywhere. Information is power, so both students and lecturers can use internet for education to make research on subjects of interest. Internet use has brought a lot of significance to undergraduate students by enhancing their academic performance and also influencing their academic behaviours as positive academic behaviour results to better academic achievements.

Internet is a worldwide system of computer networks, a network of networks in which users at any one computer can get information from any other computer if given the permission (and sometimes talk directly to users at other computers). In view of this, to connect to the internet via a range of device, desktop and laptop computers, mobile phones and tablets are the most commonly used devices. One of the roles of the internet in education has been identified as the provision of instant access to available information around the world. Education could be provided remotely across the world through the medium of internet and its resources. Traditional learning and teaching processes are changing due to the plethora of information available through internet resources. Lecturers and students both have instant access to the information on virtually any topic or subject.

Several studies have been conducted in different places of the world. The study about use of Internet for academic purpose conducted at the University of Carnegie Mellon in America where result indicated that more than 73% of the respondents go on Google for searching their academic information other study showed that most students use internet for academic as well as social connection (George 2006 and Rena 2007). The Internet is a worldwide phenomenon which has connected the globe. Moreover, Laite (2016) surveyed 406 undergraduate students from Shippensburg University, the survey showed that 57.6% of the undergraduate surveyed used the Internet 1-2 times per week and another 37.1% used it 1-2 times daily. However, some students may use the internet to communicate with friends and families through available social applications and other networking sites.

Researchers have suggested that using the internet for non-academic purposes (e.g., leisure, entertainment, socializing) displaces time that could be used for academics (Huston, Wright, Marquis, & Green, 2019). In other words, watching a movie online or chatting with friends over social media may be more entertaining and less mentally tasking for college students and therefore chosen as an activity in place of academics. As a result, assignments are not completed on time or at all, examinations are not prepared for and grades drop. The internet therefore has influence on the academic behaviour of students. Studies have shown that access to internet has birthed some technological behaviour, such as not visiting the library, not attending night classes, cheating, not attending classes, procrastination, not doing assignments etc. Due to the easy access to documents and historical background or origin on the internet, students prefer to seat in the comfort of their hostels and homes and browse out these documents rather than visiting the library to read textbooks and journals. In a study conducted in University of Malaysia Sarawak, It was indicated that students are supposed to learn how to use the internet for collecting the information about latest research (Hong, 2013). Despite the widespread belief that the use of internet in education is generally good, such may not always be the case. Burbules and Callister (2012) suggest that internet can be used well or poorly, and thus its effectiveness is dependent on how it is used, by whom and for what purpose. Although the motivation may differ, theoretically the overall expectation is that the use of internet will improve the course, engage the students and enable them to learn more. There may also be at least the implicit hope by the faculty member that teaching evaluations will improve. Clearly, utilization of internet can impact several of these identified characteristics or traits. Thus, in recent years, the proliferation of internet use in an educational setting has sparked considerable interest on the part of researchers, and a number of studies have focused on the positives and negatives of internet use from the

perspectives of the institution, student and professor. To make proper use of internet in schools, colleges and universities there is a need to understand the attitudes of students towards the use of it. For the student's attitude toward Internet applications, college and university administration should know the purposes for which students are using it whether for entertainment and sports, for academic purposes, business and social purposes, etc. Increasingly, colleges of education and universities are investing in internet service, they are also making its teaching materials available online. While colleges and universities and academics are trying to build the Internet as a valuable learning tool, it is necessary to understand the attitudes of their students' towards the use of internet and its applications.

Several studies have been conducted on attitudes of students towards utilization of the internet in different parts of the world including Nigeria. However, this study is different from previous studies because it seeks to examine the attitudes of undergraduates in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku, in Affiliation with University of Calabar towards utilization of the internet as no study relating to this topic has been carried out within the Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku, Rivers State.

In Nigeria, Anunobi (2006) revealed that 81% of students at Federal University of Technology Owarri, Nigeria, used Internet for academic purposes as compared to 15% who used it for entertainment purposes. Adekunmisi, Ajala and Iyoro (2013) in a survey on Internet access and usage by undergraduate students of Olabisi Onabanjo University, Nigeria posited that majority of the respondents used the Internet for personal communication purposes, for leisure/entertainment, for general knowledge and for current news. Fasae and Aladeniyi (2012) in a survey in two Nigerian Universities on Internet use by students found that out of the total number of students, 78% of them used the Internet for communication purposes, 89% for educational purposes and 58% for entertainment purposes. Buhari (2013) found that undergraduates used the Internet purposely for e-mail (17.2%), for information (16.2%), for conduct of research (29.0%) and for entertainment (2.6%).

Statement of the problem

In spite of the widely perceived use of the Internet by students of higher institution of learning in Nigerian universities, colleges of education and others, psychologist and educators have noted the negative impacts of its misuse, especially the problematic Internet use which is generally termed Internet addiction. However, it is not necessary that the influence of the Internet is always positive, as it might take an opposite direction. Despite the educational and social benefits of internet use, there are risks associated with its use, particularly for students in tertiary institutions. For instance, internet addiction has grown rapidly and is affecting more students. Researchers also found out that excessive use of internet leads to a decline in study habits resulting in a gradual drop in academic grades, delaying assessment task leading to procrastination and skipping of lectures due to the fact that students don't get enough sleep because much of the sleep time is spent online (Young & Rogers, cited in Akhter, 2013). Akhter (2013).

Due to the remarkable development and impact of technology that has been witnessed in the educational system especially in computers and internet, there is a dire need to study the attitude of undergraduates towards utilization of internet in Federal College of Education, Omoku in Affiliation with University of Uyo Degree Programme.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of the study is to investigate the relationship between digital literacy and undergraduates' Attitude towards utilization of the internet in Federal College of Education, Omoku in Affiliation with University of Uyo Degree Programme. Specifically, the study intends to:

1. To assess undergraduate students attitude in browsing term paper assignment and utilization of internet in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku
2. To find out the undergraduate students attitude in watching videos on the utilization of internet in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku

Research questions

The following research questions are raised to guide the study:

1. Does the utilization of internet influence undergraduate student's attitude in writing their term paper assignment in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku?

2. How does the utilization of internet influence undergraduate student's attitude in watching videos in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku?

Statement of hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

1. There is no significant influence of the utilization of attitude in browsing term paper assignment on utilization of internet by undergraduate students Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku
2. Undergraduate students attitude in watching videos has no significant influence on the use of internet in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive survey research design with the population of 2450 final year undergraduate students from Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku. Out of this population, the study sampled 250 respondents using stratified random sampling technique. The basis of stratification was based on the five major schools that are involves in degree programme. After dividing the school into schools, 3 schools were chosen given a representation of the total population. The researcher assigns a number to each school in each ward. After shaken the wrapped papers in a container, 3 wrapped paper was picked and unwrapped to identify the school selected from the schools. This process was done in all 3 until the required number of schools was drawn. The process was done to select the number of respondents. The main instrument for data collection was a self-structure questionnaire titled; Undergraduate Students Attitude in Internet Usage Questionnaire (USAIUQ). The instrument was validated by two experts in test and measurement from Federal Colleges of Education (Technical), Omoku, an affiliate of University of Uyo and was adjudge to have both content and face validity. The instrument were pilot tested using 50 respondents outside the study sampled. Four point rating scale of Strongly Agreed = 4 points, Agreed = 3 points, Disagreed = 2 points and Strongly Disagreed =1 point was used to code the items in the questionnaire. Information elicited from the instrument were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions with benchmark of 2.50.

RESULTS

Research question one: *Does the utilization of internet influence undergraduate student's attitude in writing their term paper assignment in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku?*

Table 1: Summary of mean and standard deviation of influence of student's attitude in writing term paper on internet usage (N=250)

Items	Statements	X	SD	Decision
1	I use the internet to get materials for my academic work.	3.42	.76	Accepted
2	I use the internet for read for my examination.	3.44	.66	Accepted
3	I use the internet for my assignments.	3.53	.69	Accepted
4	I use the internet to get project materials.	2.60	.88	Accepted
5	I use the internet to get new information about my area of specialization.	2.30	.55	Rejected
CLUSTER MEAN		3.26	.75	Accepted

Result from table one which sought for respondent's opinion on utilization of internet influence undergraduate student's attitude in writing their term paper assignment in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku reveal that all the items were accepted except item five with mean score of 2.30. The table also indicated that item three has the highest score of 3.53, followed by item two with 3.44. All other item including the cluster mean of 3.26 were found to be greater than the benchmark of 2.50. This implies that undergraduate student's attitude in writing term paper assignment influences their utilization of internet facilities in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku.

Research question two: *How does the utilization of internet influence undergraduate student's attitude in watching videos in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku?*

Table 2: Summary of mean and standard deviation of influence of student's attitude in watching videos on internet usage (N=250)

Items	Statements	X	SD	Decision
6	I only go to the internet to watch films and videos.	2.68	.82	Accepted
7	I only go to the internet to listen to recent musics.	3.22	.74	Accepted
8	I only go to the internet for blogging.	2.80	.90	Accepted
9	I only go to the internet to watch comedy.	2.54	.86	Accepted
10	I only go to the internet to see new fashion.	3.36	.85	Accepted
CLUSTER MEAN		2.92	.84	Accepted

Result from table one which sought for respondent's opinion on utilization of internet influence undergraduate student's attitude in watching videos in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku reveal that all the items were accepted. The table also indicated that item ten has the highest score of 3.36, followed by item seven with 3.22. All other item including the cluster mean of 2.92 were found to be greater than the benchmark of 2.50. This implies that utilization of internet influence undergraduate student's attitude in watching videos in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

From the statistics and analysis reviewed, using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation, the respondent opinion shows that undergraduate attitudes towards utilization of the internet influences their writing term paper assignment in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku, Degree Programme in Affiliation with University of Uyo. This was because the calculated mean score and standard deviation were found to be greater than the benchmark of 2.50. This finding agreed with Anunobi (2006) who reported that 81% of students at Federal University of Technology Owarri, Nigeria, used Internet for academic purposes as compared to 15% who used it for entertainment purposes. This implies that undergraduate student passion for their academic excellences will naturally influences their usage of internet for academic purposes to achieve results.

From the statistical analysis of the study second variable which sought for respondents opinion on undergraduate attitudes towards utilization of the internet influences their addition to watching videos in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku Degree Programme in Affiliation with University of Uyo, reveals a significant influence using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation, the respondent. This was because the calculated mean score and standard deviation were found to be greater than the benchmark of 2.50. This finding is in line with view of Ajala and Iyoro (2013) that posited that majority of the respondents used the Internet for personal communication purposes, for leisure/entertainment, for general knowledge and for current news. This means that during their leisure, they engage themselves in internet usage either in the phones of school cyber café to either watching movies of communicate with friends in Facebooks, WHATSAPP, Instagram and others.

CONCLUSION

This research study has been carried out essentially to know the influence of digital literacy on attitudes of undergraduates towards utilization of the internet using Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku in Affiliation with the University of Uyo as the focus of the study. With this research, it has been revealed that majority of the undergraduates of Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku in Affiliation with the University of Uyo are experienced with the use of internet, and digital literacy go a long way in influencing undergraduates' attitude towards using the internet for different purposes such as academic, communication, entertainment and others. Further it was also revealed that digital literacy influences internet addiction on undergraduates.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, a number of issues have to be addressed so that the students would avail themselves of the benefits accruing from Internet use especially good social and for academic purposes. It is in line with this that the following recommendations were made:

1. From the study it was observed that there is high level of digital literacy among undergraduates of the college. Therefore, the college authorities should improve the quality of the internet services in the college and provide proper and thorough orientation on the necessity of internet knowledge, skills and application for students, so that they can gain from the massive benefits accrued to internet utilization.
2. Furthermore, in order to improve on the academic activities of undergraduates through the use of digital services and internet, the institutions should ensure that information regarding the relevant and contemporary academic websites with their addresses be displayed on departmental notice boards, their libraries and lecture rooms.
3. The research revealed that the undergraduates use the internet for various purposes like for academic, communication, economic and information purposes. As the usage rate of internet increases day by day, so the students should eliminate the negative attitude towards internet.

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